

Semiotics of Music. The Five Features of the Fundamental Structure of Language According to Hjelmslev: Verification within the Musical System through a Harmonic-Functional Perspective

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1. Expression Plane and Content Plane

To the well-known distinction made by Umberto Eco between *code* and *code-system*, we might correspond—aiming to delimit the field and justify the chosen methodology—two different approaches to the semiotic study of music. These approaches entail differing considerations regarding the possibility and modalities through which music can signify—that is, in what way music functions as a sign, or more precisely, what semiotic modalities are found in the musical phenomenon—as well as regarding the relevant levels of analysis in a musical text.

Neutral analyses concern themselves with the autonomous organization of only one of the two planes: that of **expression**. This autonomous organization corresponds precisely to what Eco terms the *code-system* or *s-code*. The pertinence criterion adopted by this type of analysis to segment a text into its constituent traits is not based on the content plane nor on the text's contracted functional uses. Analyses that instead deal with the s-code on the content plane have traditionally fallen under the purview of psychology and theoretical sociology and are not considered here.

Before addressing the definitions of the link between the two planes, we wish to introduce the concept of **sense**, understood here as the set of relations that a unit establishes with other units within a system. It follows that **sense in music** relies on the **syntactic functions** contracted by the parts of a chain, and is determined by the deviation that may occur relative to the function a part was “expected” to fulfill. This type of relationship between parts seems, with its own specific modalities and characteristics, to hold **prognostic value**. Although we cannot claim that a consequent is logically inferred from a precedent—since we do not observe genuine cases of *rection*—musical language does appear to rely on a system of culturally determined expectations, grounded in the greater or lesser **probability** that one part of the chain will be followed by another.

Research on musical codes aims to define the convention that connects the **expression plane** to the **content plane**. Our goal is to investigate the nature of this link: in what ways and from what perspectives does such a link exist? Whenever we seek in music a **semiotic correlation**, whether dictionary-based or not, the results are understandably disappointing. Such correlations between the two planes in music occur only in a limited range of cases, mainly reducible to the **use of music as a signal**.

One way to overcome this problem could be to consider **meaning** in **Peircean** terms of **interpretability**: evaluating the capacity of music to be interpreted—meaning, the possibility for a signifier to be translated into another signifier, called the *interpretant*, which “broadens its understanding” (Eco, 1984, p. 51)—as a sufficient condition to speak of musical meaning. In fact, music allows for one signifier to be substituted by another, as in the case of a **melody transposed** to another key, or its restatement with **altered timbral parameters**. Yet, in both cases, the **intervallic relationships** remain unchanged, and we encounter the kind of **conformity** that, according to Hjeltmslev’s classification, characterizes **monoplanar systems**. These systems “although interpretable like other semiotic systems (...) are characterized by the fact that (...) the semantic interpretation reproduces the same articulations and can be represented according to the same rules as the interpreted form” (Greimas, 1986, p. 182).

The difficulty in correlating a set of notes with the content plane undermines the possibility of recognizing **double articulation** in the musical system. While the identification of the **distinctive features** that constitute a note reveals a certain similarity between natural language and music, the same cannot be said regarding the **first articulation**, due to the difficulty, as already mentioned, in assigning sequences a **distinctive function** comparable to that of words in language.

Even at the level of the **second articulation**, specific issues arise: the features commonly considered distinctive of a note—**pitch, intensity, timbre, duration**—when examined outside a contextual frame, behave (with the exception of pitch) more like **variants**. In language, for instance, the phonemes *T* and *D* differ by their distinctive traits: *T* is dental, plosive, voiceless; *D* is dental, plosive, voiced—so the distinctive trait is voicing. In music, two isolated notes like *C* and *D* are distinguished by **pitch**, but when other traits vary, the identity of the notes appears preserved. It is their **intervallic relationship** that defines them.

Evidently, the question must be reframed: since notes contract functions within a context, certain traits must be rendered **pertinent** over others depending on the **analytical perspective** adopted. For example, an analysis aiming to determine the **melodic syntax** in

the chorale repertoire of **J.S. Bach** will treat **duration, position, and scale degree** as relevant traits, while traits like timbre and intensity are deemed non-pertinent (cf. Baroni – Jacoboni, 1976).

In the sections that follow, we will refer primarily to the **classical repertoire** and thus will consider **pitch**, or more precisely the **intervallic relationship** between chords and between the notes within a chord, as a **pertinent trait**.

2. Process and System

The second trait discussed by Louis Hjelmslev is “the ability to distinguish, in a given phenomenon, the *system* from its *process*.” Evidently, what appears visible in a phenomenon is its **processual aspect**, whereas the **systematic aspect** consists of the inventory of constant elements—taken once and for all—that reappear in an order which, in the inductive phase, is determined by the process itself (Zinna, 1985, p. V).

It is therefore clear that analysis must begin with the **process**, with the relations present in the **syntagmatic chain**, and from there derive the **paradigms**, that is, the classes of elements capable of occupying a certain position in the chain. In other words, the system is *inferred* from the process. If it is possible to distinguish the system from the process in the musical phenomenon, then we should be able to verify that a certain sequence is the **syntagmatic arrangement** of elements occupying specific positions because they belong to the **same class**.

The **tonal-harmonic system**, as is well known, is fundamentally based on three **functions**: tonic, subdominant, and dominant. These functions are **paradigmatic classes** of members—in this case, chords built on scale degrees—that are eligible to occupy specific positions in the process, as defined by the **syntagmatic relations** these functions establish with each other. The **standardized sequence** within tonal-harmonic language—Tonic > Subdominant > Dominant > Tonic—regulates the relationship among parts of the process.

FUNZIONI	T	SD	D	T
	Accordo di I	Accordo di IV	Accordo di V	Accordo di I
	Accordo di VI	Accordo di II	Accordo di III	Accordo di VI
	Accordo di III	Accordo di VI	Accordo di VII	Accordo di III

As the schematic representation shows, degrees I, VI, and III are **functionives** that contract the tonic function. Among these, the VI degree is notable in that it also belongs to another paradigm, that of the **subdominant**. Thus, the chord built on the sixth degree, having the potential to contract different functions and thereby occupy different positions in the process, is of a **bivalent** nature. Since the bivalent chord is part of an **enunciation**, its **disambiguation** through **paradigmatic disjunction** is determined by the “co-textual pressure realized syntagmatically” (Eco, 1979, p. 9). In the following example, the VI-degree chord, preceded by a V-degree chord and followed by a I-degree chord, contracts the **tonic function**, even though the subdominant function remains a **potential valency** of the same chord.

Example 1

The image shows a musical score for Example 1 in G major (one sharp). The top staff is in treble clef with a common time signature (C). The bottom staff is in bass clef with a common time signature (C). The sequence of chords is: I (C major), IV (D major), V (E major), VI (F major), and I (C major). The chords are represented by block chords in the treble clef and single notes in the bass clef. The labels I, IV, V, VI, and I are placed below the bass staff.

However, **contextual selections** are only possible within **well-defined historical and cultural contexts**, and must refer to **consolidated syntactic codes**. For this reason, our discussion focuses on the repertoire that conforms to **tonal-harmonic grammar**; this choice also justifies the **privileged attention** paid to **pitch** as a **distinctive feature** (cf. Chapter 1: Expression and Content).

In language, **polysemy** exists—except in cases of **multiple isotopy**—only in a **virtual state**: the appearance of a lexeme in an enunciation disambiguates it, activating one of its sememes (Greimas, 1986, p. 256). In music, however, it is quite common for a **single functionive** to realize **two different functions** within the same chain. This mechanism is at play in **modulation**, or the passage from one key to another.

For instance, a **I-degree chord in C major** is also the **V-degree chord in F major**. This chord may thus contract the **tonic function** in C and the **dominant function** in F. In Example 1, the **context** realizes only one of these two functions. In other cases—such as in **Example 2**—a kind of **syntactic multiple isotopy** occurs, where the **same chord**

simultaneously fulfills distinct functions in relation to both the preceding and following parts of the chain.

Example 2

Example 2 shows a musical progression in two systems. The first system is labeled 'DO' and the second 'FA'. The progression consists of five chords: I, V, I in DO / V in FA, V7, and I. The chords are shown in both treble and bass clefs. The first system has a treble clef and a bass clef. The second system has a treble clef and a bass clef. The chords are: I (C major), V (G major), I in DO / V in FA (C major / G major), V7 (G7), and I (C major).

Another case of interest is that of **wandering chords**. The **diminished seventh chord**, made up of three stacked minor thirds, is emblematic of this category. Built on the **raised seventh degree** of the minor scale, it can—thanks to its peculiar construction and enharmonic interpretability—belong to **four different minor keys** while still contracting the same **dominant function**. In the next example, the **fourth chord** in the progression performs the **same function** (dominant) in both **A minor** and **C minor**.

Example 3

Example 3 shows a musical progression in two systems. The first system is labeled '(LA -)' and the second '(DO -)'. The progression consists of five chords: I, V, I, VII, and I. The chords are shown in both treble and bass clefs. The first system has a treble clef and a bass clef. The second system has a treble clef and a bass clef. The chords are: I (C major), V (G major), I (C major), VII (F# diminished), and I (C major).

3. Commutation Test

The **commutation test** is the central trait of Louis Hjelm's theoretical framework. It enables six fundamental functions, among which is that of rigorously defining **semisymbolic systems** (Zinna, 1985). Given that music is a **monoplanar system** (cf. Chapter 5), the

commutation test—since it determines the relationship between the **planes** and **axes** of language—loses much of its **heuristic value** in this context.

Nonetheless, the commutation test **has found**, and can still find, important applications in music. Especially when conceived in **phonological terms**, it can be used to identify in general the **pertinent features** of a musical passage in relation to the musical system to which it belongs. For example, in Bruno Nettl's essay "*De quelques méthodes linguistiques appliquées à l'analyse musicale*", published in *Musique en jeu*, no. 5, he explains how in the **Arapaho culture**, the difference between a quarter note and a dotted quarter note is **not a pertinent trait**—just as in the **minor mode** of Western music, the difference between the **natural sixth degree** and its **raised form** may not be pertinent either.

There are also other examples in which the commutation test proves effective in identifying **pertinent** and **non-pertinent traits** within the tonal-harmonic system. Every pianist, for instance, **inadvertently performs a commutation test** when playing **The Well-Tempered Clavier** by J.S. Bach—commonly performed even in concert settings—thereby demonstrating that **timbre** may be considered a **non-pertinent trait** for that repertoire. The same holds for other musical parameters: for example, when a conductor decides to interpret a piece at a faster or slower tempo. Even a singer, when not in top form, may **transpose** an aria down by a semitone or a whole tone. This is possible because, although the **key** of a piece still serves to label countless symphonic and instrumental works, it may in fact **not** be a **pertinent trait** in the **tempered tonal-harmonic system**. What "counts," so to speak—what is *pertinent*—is the **interval**, the **intervallic relation**, not the **absolute pitch**, since in the **tempered system** the relationships between degrees maintain the **same cent-based differences** across all keys.

As Luca Marconi notes in the introduction to *Il senso in musica*, there exists a **functional approach** to music studies—such as that of **Gino Stefani**—which is oriented toward recognizing the **relationships between structure and function**, i.e., identifying pertinent traits relative to the **social use** or **external function** that a musical piece fulfills. Changing a single **formal element** of a musical piece may indeed change its function. For instance, in certain contexts, **changing the tempo** from fast to slow may transform a song from a **dance tune** to a **sentimental ballad** (Sychra, 1948). In our view, this approach is clearly traceable to the **basic mechanism** of **Hjelmslev's commutation test**.

A way of understanding and using the commutation test even more in line with **glossematics**—although strictly speaking impossible—arises when applying the **syntagmatic approach to harmonic functions**. As previously discussed (cf. Section 2: Process and System), harmonic functions can be seen as **classes of members** that can

occupy the same position in the chain and are thus **paradigmatically interchangeable**. One can attempt to **substitute chords** that are members of the same class and observe what changes occur at the **functional-harmonic level**.

Restricting this operation to this sole point of view, we may attempt to identify **variants** and **invariants**. In classical music, for example, it appears possible to **commute** the I degree with the VI degree for the **Tonic function**, and to consider VI and I as **invariants**, just as we may regard the **seventh chords** built on these degrees as **variants**.

Of course, the issue of **conformity**, especially at the level of such a **structurally codified** trait as harmony, **relativizes** the above considerations. Still, within certain **genres** and **historical periods**, our **functional approach** proves more effective and justified—such as in **Baroque music**, where many ornaments were improvised, or in **jazz**. In **basso continuo**, that is, the harmonization of a vocal or instrumental piece for organ or harpsichord, the **invariants** were the I, IV, and V chords—such that even the most adventurous improvisation could be reduced to their succession and still fulfill its **structuring role**. We are thus led to consider all **substitutable chords** as **variants** of these core functions.

In **jazz**, this phenomenon seems even more evident. A prototypical jazz piece like “*I Got Rhythm*” (cf. harmonic scheme in Section 4) may be **harmonically reinterpreted** in dozens of different ways, with derived chords far more complex than the previously mentioned sevenths—yet the piece remains **recognizable** in its identity. This example—which involves not only **harmonic** but also **melodic improvisation**—suggests even more than basso continuo that the true **invariants** of the tonal-harmonic system are the chords built on the **I, IV, and V degrees**, which **Yizhak Sadai** calls the “*représentants principaux*” of the T, SD, and D functions. Based on this, we study **syntagmatic relations**, such as **combination** and **government**, by adopting a **functional-harmonic perspective**, extending it to the segmentation of the process into so-called **functional syntagms** (Sadai, 1986). Thus, we refer to:

- **T-functional syntagm**: a succession of tonic chords or tonic-related chords;
- **SD-functional syntagm**: a succession of chords orbiting around the subdominant, typically separated by a fourth or fifth in the bass from the previous syntagm;
- **D-functional syntagm**: a succession of chords orbiting around the dominant, similarly marked by a fourth or fifth shift from the prior unit.

4. Combination and Government (Rection)

The fourth fundamental trait of the basic structure of language is the presence of well-defined **relations between linguistic units**, known as **combination** and **government** (or *rection*). **Combination** refers to a relation between **two variables**, while **government** refers to a relation between **a variable and a constant** (in which case it is **unilateral**), or between **two constants** (in which case it is **reciprocal**). In music, **combination** and **government**, as relations between parts of the **chain** that constitutes the process, assume a crucial **heuristic importance**—even greater than that which Hjelmslev attributes to these traits in *passé-partout* systems, compared to the other four traits.

We have noted in earlier chapters that **musical sense arises** from the structuring of sound material into a process that unfolds part by part. That is, music demonstrates the triumph of what the **Stoics** had already identified as a fundamental mechanism of **semiosis: prognosis**. Meaning in music, therefore, does not arise from **equivalence** or **correlation** between expression and content—as it does in sign systems—but rather from **inference**, from the **relations (combination and government)** contracted by the parts of a chain, and from the **realization or non-realization** of a prognosticated event. Thus, it is **combination and government** that allow us to explain and analyze the **sense** of a musical piece.

In music, **true government (rection)** in the linguistic sense does not exist; that is, there is no evident functional case in which the **presence of one unit is a necessary condition for the presence of another**, as happens in natural languages (e.g., in Italian, where *q* is necessarily followed by *u*).

Even in the most rigid s-codes, like the **serial system**, it is true that the twelve tones within the octave follow the fixed order of the series, but it is also true that **each pitch**, outside the series—within harmonies or transitional phases—may appear **without being preceded or followed by its adjacent tone** in the series.

Nevertheless, every musical s-code—and we refer here to the **tonal-harmonic** one—is structured upon dependencies that, if not strictly **governmental**, are at least **probabilistic** in nature. Based on this premise, since the 1960s, music has been linked to **information theory**. It has been studied as a **Markov stochastic process**: a probabilistic process in which the probabilities of occurrence **depend on previous events** in the chain, and which can be translated quantitatively in terms of **redundancy, entropy, information, and feedback**.

Before delving into how these two seemingly distant domains have converged, let us briefly examine some of the **relations that structure the tonal-harmonic system**. **At the melodic level**, it is based on a **tonal center**, the **Tonic**, which combines with all other degrees but is necessarily implied by the **leading tone (seventh degree)**. **At the harmonic level**, the chord built on the **V degree** (Dominant function) **resolves to the Tonic**, forming the **fundamental harmonic progression**—the *ur-satz*, in Heinrich Schenker's terms—of Western music from the late Baroque to the early 20th century, and still present in much popular music today. **Seventh chords**, composed of four stacked thirds, must resolve **a fifth down or a fourth up**. In terms of **musical forms**, for example within the **sonata form**, we observe a well-structured progression of sections: **Exposition** = First theme (home key) – Modulating bridge – Second theme (dominant key) – Recapitulation; **Development** = Harmonic, melodic, and rhythmic elaboration of the exposition material; **Recapitulation** = Both themes in the original key. In this sense, the **sonata form** can be interpreted as a **modal process**, in which “the listener is guided through various modal zones on the basis of their competence” (Tarasti, 1983, p. 7). The list could continue with many **grammatical and formal rules** made explicit in harmony manuals or simply internalized through **repertoire competence**. As we explained earlier (cf. Section 2: Process and System), our analytical perspective **does not focus on melodic, rhythmic, or formal levels**, but rather on the **harmonic level**. In particular, we adopt a **syntagmatic-paradigmatic approach** to the analysis of **harmonic functions**, applying the concept of **functional syntagm** to segment a piece and study its internal relations (cf. Section 3: Commutation Test).

Let us return to **information theory**. In a text published several years ago on aesthetics and information theory, we find the now classic contribution by musicologist **Leonard Meyer**, who was among the first to explain **musical meaning** in terms of **expectation and inference**. His contribution allows us to illustrate how **quantifying the information** of a piece using **Shannon and Weaver's formula** presupposes the **analysis of combinations and governments** that structure a given text. Meyer explains: “If a situation is highly organized and the probable outcomes of a given module are highly predictable, the information content is low; conversely, if the situation is characterized by a high degree of fluidity, where the outcomes are more or less equally probable, the information is said to be high.” (Meyer, 1957, p. 161)

From this passage, and recalling that *information* means “the degree of freedom one has in constructing a message,” we can deduce the following: Where there is **combination**, expectations are weak, information is high, and emotional involvement is low; Where **government is realized**, information is low but expectation is strong, and **embodied meaning** is weak; Where **government is not realized**, information is extremely high and the trait in question becomes highly **significant**—in other words, interesting, stimulating, and even “pleasurable.”

We have observed that **music lacks strict government** as seen in *passe-partout* languages, because musical s-codes are never rigid, but instead exhibit **probabilistic regularity**. As **Ruwet** suggests, a musical work—like a poem—**generates its own code**, of which it is the **sole message**.

However, as already discussed in the context of harmonic functions, we can verify that at the level of **functional syntagms**, the cycle **T–SD–D–T** assumes such strong structural value in the classical repertoire that we may speak—albeit in a probabilistic sense—of **government (rektion)**.

Adopting this perspective—which isolates, we reiterate, the **harmonic parameter**, excluding melodic, rhythmic, and formal ones—we observe the following **governmental tendencies** among syntagms: the **D-functional syntagm** has a **unilateral rektion** relationship with the **T-functional syntagm**: it implies T but is not necessarily implied by it.

The **SD-functional syntagm** implies D, though less rigidly (consider, for example, the **plagal cadence IV–I**). The **T-functional syntagm** is the **constant**, the **necessary presence** for the appearance of other functions.

Clearly, the **strongest rektion** is between **D and T**, and it is upon this relationship that the **modulation process**—which most enriches the harmonic meaning of a piece—is based (cf. Section 2: Process and System). Modulation always occurs through a chord that has **dominant function**, and thus always takes place **within a D syntagm** or **creates one by its presence**. Without going into detailed analysis of specific works—which is beyond the scope of this paper—we maintain that a simple **listening** of any classical piece is sufficient to observe, in the score, that the **most stimulating and meaningful harmonic moments**—precisely because they are **ambiguous, unexpected, and unpredictable**—are those in which **modulation** occurs. An emblematic D-functional syntagm in classical operatic and symphonic music is the so-called “**bravura cadence**”: at the end of an aria or concerto, the soloist, over a **dominant chord**, improvises to showcase technical skill, creating a D syntagm of discretionary length, but in which the **Tonic (T)** is absolutely indispensable.

Another particularly significant phenomenon, in terms of government, is how the **tonal-harmonic system in the 19th century expanded and eventually undermined itself**, playing on the **wandering (suspended) D function**. This is exemplified by the succession of **diminished sevenths, augmented fifths, and altered chords** (like the “Tristan chord”), which—due to their harmonic structure (cf. Section 2)—can be interpreted as belonging to and resolving in **multiple keys**, and which, through their continual succession and lack of resolution, **evoke and deny the D–T rektion** endlessly.

In some **popular music repertoires**, we find an **analogous harmonic structure**, though with particular features. In these cases, the **functional cycle** is always respected, the

structure is **repeated consistently** throughout the piece, and **modulation is virtually absent**, except occasionally in the **B section** of **AABA-form songs**.

According to **L. Faether** in *Inside Jazz*, the two **fundamental chord schemes** upon which about half of all jazz pieces—from the genre’s origins to Bebop—are based, are **precise realizations** of the **T–SD–D–T cycle**:

- The **blues progression** can be translated into functional syntagms as follows:

- The **I Got Rhythm** progression is:

As we can see, in these musical domains the functional cycle is **never avoided** or broken—it is **repeated continuously** for the entire length of the piece.

5. (Non)-Conformity

The **expression plane and content plane**, the **axis of system** and the **axis of process**, as well as the phenomena of **combination** and **government**, are the three traits that are common to all systems—whether symbolic or genuinely semiotic. By contrast, the **commutation test** and the condition of **conformity or non-conformity** are used by Hjelmslev to **typologize** these systems.

As discussed in the first chapter (cf. *1. Expression Plane and Content Plane*), the search for a **double articulation** in the musical system presents insurmountable problems. In particular, we wish to emphasize the **impossibility of identifying minimal units** that

correspond to **phonemes** in natural language. In this regard, Nicolas Ruwet observes: “On the level of language, phonemes—that is, the elements that serve to distinguish meaning—do not themselves have meaning. One must therefore distinguish between the level of phonemes and that of morphemes. By contrast, in music there is only one level: the elements and the groups they distinguish are of the same nature.” (Ruwet, 1972, p. 12)

We have examined the **syntactic behavior** of the musical system and, in particular, verified the existence of a **system regulating syntagmatic processes**. On one hand, we found that **paradigms**—that is, **classes of members** capable of occupying a certain position in the chain—do exist. On the other hand, we must stress that **every paradigmatic substitution results in a change of meaning**.

From this perspective, both **Baroque** and **jazz music** would merit a dedicated study (cf. 3. *Commutation Test*).

Based on these premises—and by defining **conformity** as “a one-to-one correspondence between the units (...) of the two planes” (Greimas, 1986, p. 74)—we may conclude that **any mutation on the expression plane** inevitably causes a **mutation of the same rank** on the content plane. Therefore, the system is **monoplanar**. In other words, the musical system is **interpretable**, but only **according to the same formal articulations** as those of the expression plane. This is why, from the very first chapter, we preferred to speak of **sense**—the relations among units in the system—rather than of **meaning**.

We believe that the peculiar characteristics which **Greimas** attributes to the link between the two planes in **poetic discourse**—marked by a certain **isomorphism** between expression categories and content categories, and thus by the **co-occurrence of forms** on both planes (Greimas, 1974, p. 292)—may be brought closer to those of the **musical system**.

This is the direction taken by **Costin Miereanu**, who, in the article “Structures profondes, structures superficielles, structures de la manifestation en musique” (*Semiotica*, vol. 66), attempted to identify **prosodic regulators** on the expression plane corresponding to the **syntactic level** on the content plane.

Continuing briefly on this connection between **poetics** and the **semiotics of music**, it is important to point out that the **equivalence relations** characteristic of poetic language (as defined by Jakobson) have been fruitfully employed by **Ruwet** to investigate the **specificity of the musical system**. Indeed, Jakobson’s well-known formulation: “The poetic function projects the principle of equivalence from the axis of selection to the axis of combination.” (Jakobson, 1972, p. 192) enabled Ruwet to define **repetition** as the **defining trait** of the musical phenomenon and the **principle of segmentation** of a text.

Based on the examination of the five traits carried out in the corresponding chapters, we may now argue that **if we are to speak of a ‘musical language’**—a term now commonly used—we must also be fully aware of the **peculiar traits** that characterize **natural languages** but are **not found** in the musical system.

We have verified that, within the **tonal-harmonic system**, it is possible to distinguish, at the syntactic level, **process from system**. However, we have also observed that the **commutation test**, understood as the operation that allows us to determine the relationship between planes and axes of the system, **has no application at the denotative level**.

We are now faced with the question of whether the description of a **connotative language**—and whether the musical system can be classified as such is an open hypothesis—should proceed through the **commutation principle on the expression plane**, or instead through the **development of a theory of connotation**, in order to: “describe connotative systems based on the content plane.” (Greimas, 1986, p. 317)

In this second case, we would be tasked with identifying the **topical dimensions** upon which **connotative activity** is applied.

Moreover, the **conformity** that we hypothesize to characterize the relationship between the two planes must itself become the object of further analysis: we must determine whether this conformity occurs at the level of **individual elements** or of **categories**.

That is, although we have supposed the system to be **monoplanar**, we still need to specify **which levels of articulation** of the expression plane **correspond to interpretation**.

A **sociosemiotic approach**, capable of defining **social connotations**, and a **psychosemiotic approach**, which defines **individual connotations**, could thus represent the most appropriate tools for developing models of: “expectation as possible loci of connotative manifestation.” (Greimas, 1986, p. 77)

This opens up **promising avenues of research** for the semiotics of music—not only by connecting **expectation** to the **listener’s cultural competence** (Stefani, 1982), but also by seeking to rigorously identify phenomena of **aspectualization**, in order to precisely distinguish between different types of **sense effects**, such as **temporality** and, indeed, **aspectuality**.

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